

STUDY OF THE PHYSICOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF MANGANESE-CONTAINING ORES

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Abstract

This goal can be achieved by increasing the efficiency of extracting valuable components and reducing energy and economic costs in subsequent stages of enrichment and processing. The processes of ore preparation for enrichment are the most energy-intensive in mineral processing plants and have a significant impact on subsequent mineral processing processes. In order to optimize the processes of preparing copper-molybdenum ores for enrichment and to study the kinetics of crushing, some studies were conducted on the ores of the "Yoshlik" deposit. To quantitatively assess the selectivity of ore preparation operations, the distribution of components by size classes was analyzed based on the results of elemental analysis and granulometric analysis.

Keywords: Kinetics, copper-molybdenum ores, selectivity index, porphyry copper deposits, phase analysis, non-ferrous metals, chalcopyrite, optimization.

Introduction. Currently, there is a decrease in the average manganese content in extracted ores and a reduction in the number of developed deposits. Therefore, enrichment of manganese-containing ores is required. Finding economically and environmentally beneficial technologies for enriching manganese-containing ores is an important direction of the mining industry.

The relevance of this work lies in considering the possibility of enriching manganese ores as a source material for obtaining high-quality manganese concentrates and subsequently using them in the production of ferroalloys in the metallurgical industry.

As in the rest of the world, manganese reserves are represented mainly by difficult-to-enrich carbonate ores (90.8%), but there are also easily processed oxide and mixed ores. In the composition of manganese ores, the manganese content is from 5 to 24%. In this regard, the development of a technology for enriching depleted manganese ores for use in steel production is of interest [1-2].

Manganese is one of the most commonly used metals for deoxidation, desulfurization, and alloying of steels. This is a silver-white metal with the following properties [3]: density - 7.21-8.44 g/cm³; hardness - 400-420 kg/mm²; specific heat capacity at 298 K - 0.478 kJ/(kg·K); thermal conductivity at 298 K - 66.57 W/(m·K); specific magnetic susceptibility - 0.6·10⁻⁶ m³/kg; specific electrical resistance - (1.5-2.6) ·10⁻⁶ Ohm·m. Manganese has oxidation states

from +2 to +7, but its most characteristic state is +2, +4, +7. In natural systems, manganese is part of the Fe-Mn-Al geochemical triad.

The material composition of manganese ores in Uzbekistan is very complex and diverse. The ores are divided into three main types: oxide, mixed, and carbonate, which in turn are subdivided into a number of mineral subtypes: psilomelane, psilomelane-pyrolusite-manganite, manganocalcite-calcium-rhodochrosite, and many others. According to their textural-structural properties, they are divided into concrete-layered, piece-yellow, earth-like, and other less common types. More than 150 manganese minerals are known, but the most common manganese minerals are: pyrolusite MnO_2 , manganite $Mn_2O_3 \cdot xH_2O$, braunite $3Mn_2O_3 \cdot xMnSiO_3$, hausmannite Mn_3O_4 , rhodochrosite ($MnCO_3$) and others[3-4].

Table 1 shows the physical properties of the main manganese minerals.

Table 1

Physical properties of basic manganese minerals

Mineral	Content of Mn, %	Density, g/cm ³	Hardness (Moos scale)	Specific magnetic susceptibility $\beta \cdot 10^5$, cm ³ /g	Melting point, °C
Pyrolusite	61-63.2	4.7-5.0	2.0-6.5	2.0 - 120	1050.
Psilomelane	44-60	4.0-4.71	4.0-6.0	3.0-87	1000
Manganite	61.5	4.2-4.33	3.5-4.0	28.2-43.0	1000
Brownite	61-69.5	4.7-5.0	6.0-6.5	90-180	12.00
Gausmanite	73.	4.7-4.9	5.0-5.5	44-280.	1567.
Vernadite	45-53.	1.8-3.3	2.0-3.0	No data	1100-1200

As can be seen from the data presented in the table, the highest manganese content in the mineral is found in hausmannite, braunite, pyrolusite, and manganite. In this case, the high-density mineral is also hausmannite. And in terms of hardness (according to the Moos scale), pyrolusite and braunite have a high value.

Thus, the physicochemical properties of manganese and manganese-containing ores were investigated, which showed the main physicochemical properties of the main manganese minerals.

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